

THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS

¹Ulugbekova Sarvinoz Zafarbek kizi

3rd year of student of NamSU, Turakurgan district

Email: sarvinozulugbekova2002@gmail.com,

²Botirova Zebo Khakimjon Kizi

PhD, senior teacher

“English language and literature” department,
Namangan State University, Uychi str., Namangan, Uzbekistan

Email: ziziko90@mail.ru, Tel: +998907507557.

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ABSTRACT

Competencies are the abilities and expertise that help teachers succeed. Teachers need to be proficient in a wide range of competences in a particularly complicated environment where hundreds of key judgments are needed each day in order to enhance student development. The article is explores teacher's professional competence, their types as linguistic, communicative, information, and technological.

The development of a foreign language teacher's desire to learn, the updating of his knowledge, the improvement of skills and competences, one of which is linguistic and vocational, are among the most crucial tasks that are being addressed today in the course of a foreign language teacher's training. The needs for a foreign language instructor have greatly expanded under the contemporary educational system. A new standard of philological and linguistic preparation for the teacher himself is necessary in light of trends to increase the general humanitarian and philological training of graduates of universities. The demand for properly qualified instructors is increasing in today's fast changing society.

First and foremost, a teacher's professional competency is tied to his capacity to address both personal and work-related issues that arise in the course of teaching. The following definition of a teacher's professional competence is found in pedagogical dictionary: «The teacher's possession of the necessary amount of knowledge, skills, and skills that determine the formation of his pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication, and the personality of the teacher as the bearer of certain values, ideals, and pedagogical consciousness».

The work of a teacher, according to A. K. Markov, is one in which educational action and pedagogical communication are carried out at a sufficiently high level, the teacher's personality is realized, and the pupils get effective instruction and upbringing. Additionally, the ratio of a teacher's professional knowledge and abilities to his professional positions and psychological traits determines the teacher's competency. When examining professional competence, author divides it into the following categories: special, personal, individual, and social. According to E. F. Zera, competency entails not only a specialist's knowledge and experience but also their capacity to apply their acquired information and abilities in the present to carry out their professional duties. Depending on the circumstance, the preparedness and capacity to use this information is crucial in this scenario.

In the current world, a teacher must continually learn, participate in self-education, and self-actualize through pedagogical practice in order to be professionally effective. The instructor engages into an appropriation-bestowal connection as part of the self-realization process. A self-fulfilling teacher not only contributes to society but also invests in the ideals of his students. A teacher in the educational system is a self-developing personality who enhances both his professional and personal attributes via ongoing self-improvement. Teacher is not just a profession, the essence of which is to transfer information, but also a lofty purpose of developing a person who affirms a person in a person, according to V. A. Slastenin, who provides the most comprehensive definition of the professionally relevant attributes of the teacher.

Any teacher should possess a broad range of professional skills. One might think of a foreign language teacher's professional competence, which combines elements like essential, fundamental, and specialized competence. The most important ones are those competencies required for all professional activities. The distinctiveness of some professional activity is reflected in the fundamental abilities. On the one hand, a professional's special expertise represents the particulars of a certain subject area. On the other hand, it is seen as the application of fundamental and crucial subject-area abilities. Thus, the proficiency of a foreign language instructor is a unique professional competency.

The following elements make up the structure of a foreign language teacher's special competence:

Communicative competence (knowledge of a foreign language with a focus on the workplace);

Linguistic competence (assuming knowledge of the basic theoretical provisions on language as a social phenomenon, its connection with thinking, the culture of the people, the origin and development of language)

Linguistic competence: (knowledge of the culture of the country where the studied language is spoken, its history, and current development issues, as well as about life, daily activities, games, popular literature, music, and movies, and the capacity to use this knowledge in deciding what to teach)

A teacher's information competence, which supplies the skills of its activity with knowledge contained in educational disciplines and educational domains, as well as in the surrounding world, cannot currently be ignored when establishing their professional competence. The interaction between the instructor and the trainee in an information environment where the communication process is done in this environment's language — its methods and technologies — is the use of information technology in the professional training of the teacher. A different kind of competence — information and technological — is the capacity to use contemporary computer and communication technologies for the purpose of interpersonal communication and workflow organization. It is required to establish specific pedagogical circumstances that will improve the information component of the courses taught by the linguist-teacher in order to build an information and technical computer. He must therefore learn the following information and abilities: to create and apply educational software in his professional and educational activities; to use systems for processing symbolic, graphic, and numerical information; remote databases; to access the Internet and

use network services; to participate in electronic conferences; to post information there; to read and "download" already existing information; and to possess real-time negotiation tools. The level of the teacher's competence will grow as a result of the knowledge and skills acquired on the basis of new didactic opportunities made possible by contemporary computer equipment and telecommunications capabilities.

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